

PEDAGOGY

METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING WORK ON TEXTS IN AZERBAIJAN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract

A teacher who develops students' listening, reading and writing skills works for the future: he forms students' abilities to read specialized scientific literature in the Azerbaijani language, to use computer support and internet facilities skillfully. This type of work, which fulfills the tasks of the professional orientation of education, helps to increase the competitiveness of the graduate. It is equally important to express the fact that the majority of students have a fairly high motivation and desire to learn English in a quality way. The current situation makes the problem of creating new technologies necessary for linguistic training of students urgent.

Currently, the amount of methodical support of the university for the subject "Azerbaijani language" has increased significantly: the published teaching, teaching, methodical and informational literature is designed to help the teacher in organizing high-quality education.

Keywords: Azerbaijani language, writing habits, linguistic, linguistic didactics, differentiation.

The materials of scientific-practical conferences on the problems of secondary school teaching, articles in scientific collections, reports and messages of Azerbaijani language teachers at conferences and seminars allow us to conclude that an active search for innovative approaches to the study of native and non-teaching science is underway. In the scientific study of linguistic didactic orientation, the strategy of acquisition of communicative competence by students is determined, and the authors refer to both normative (grammatical) and communicative (correct speech) aspects.

The analysis of the published material shows that teachers pay serious attention to issues related to teaching students speech activities such as production, listening, reading, and not enough attention is paid to learning problems related to teaching students to write in the Azerbaijani language. At the same time, this type of speech activity can be used both as a goal and as a means of learning: the writing process greatly contributes to the mastery of monologue speech, the development of features such as expansion, consistency and logic in students.

The Internet has expanded the possibilities of business and personal correspondence with native speakers, which in turn has led to the desire to master not only oral, but also written speech. The urgent need to define the nature and characteristics of written speech in Azerbaijani, and to describe teaching-methodical support for its development, is thus determined.

Learning to write is carried out in the process of mastering a set of relevant knowledge, speech skills and communication skills necessary for creating speech. In this regard, the formation of speech competence is related to the improvement of all types of speech activity, but in practice we are faced with the predominance of speech and reading, not only writing, but also insufficient attention to the formation of skills.

As the analysis of workbooks and students' written work of high school students shows, the tasks they perform are often associated with the reproductive level of cognitive activity: these are analytical exercises, complex copying or design of texts prepared for retelling.

Most of the students do not have the ability to create their own texts.

Today, written speech communication is especially in demand, which shows the relevance of the problem of researching new ways of teaching students to write in the Azerbaijani language.

From the point of view of modern methodology, the writing process should be considered as a creative process of creating one's own expression, a productive act of mental activity, during which the student learns to form his own thoughts, choose his own thoughts, determine the dose and organize them.

Therefore, in the practice of university education, writing is an important methodological tool: in order to perfectly master the student's writing skills, the grammar of the English language, the sound-letter relationships that are quite specific in it, as well as spelling. Working on writing helps to strengthen knowledge of English vocabulary and grammar, and to develop reading skills and abilities.

In addition, writing can serve as an objective method to monitor students' knowledge and skills in the Azerbaijani language. Modern writing methodology is based on the synthesis of linguistic (learning lexical and grammatical rules based on knowledge of the laws of language) and psychophysiological (developing sensorimotor skills), learning lexical and grammatical rules and basics.

This approach explains the appeal to a fairly popular type of exercise in school and university practice - cheating. Today, falsification is considered as an effective technique in the formation of error-free writing habits in linguistic didactics, as the basis of a whole system of training exercises, which includes various tasks for generalization and differentiation.

There is no doubt about the rationality of using spelling in acquiring writing habits in the Azerbaijani language. Teaching dictation plays the role of an effective tool in the teacher's work: students have additional opportunities not only to hear the correct pronunciation of words, to pay attention to the features of the structure

of individual phrases and sentences, but also to learn examples that will help them.

It is easy to see that independently constructed and written texts are created by pronunciation of individual language units in a characteristic manner for spelling. The difference is only in who pronounces the text - the writer himself or the teacher. Therefore, spellings are an effective way to prepare students to write self-generated expressions.

Instructional spelling can be taught without changing the text and by changing the form of the material being spelled. The first group of dictations includes: warning, explanation and comment letter. For dictation, the teacher selects the words that make up the lexical minimum of the topic, as well as the text whose paradigmatic includes the language units studied in this section.

The text, which is small in volume and interesting in content, is spelled by students without modification. The analysis of the sections included in it is not organized in the same way. Consider the characteristics of each of these spells.

Less useful for mastering writing skills in the Azerbaijani language will be to resort to dictation by changing the text. The most effective of them are selective and creative dictations. Selective dictation can be used when working on mastering not only spelling rules, but also various grammatical topics.

When using it, a coherent text containing sufficient examples of the language phenomenon being studied is presented, and students are asked to identify these examples by ear and make appropriate notes.

Creative spelling comes in many varieties and can be used in any lesson. For example, when conducting vocabulary work, the teacher offers the students a semantic description of a certain lexical unit, and the students write the word that expresses it. Another example: the teacher dictates the nouns, and the students themselves choose and write definitions that match their meaning.

More complex types of tasks for creative spelling can be associated with the inclusion of a certain syntactic unit in the sentence structure or the replacement of one form of the verb with another.

Different methods can be used to organize dictionary spelling. Work on the formation of students' passive and active vocabulary is carried out in each lesson and

involves expanding their vocabulary, which consists of understanding the meaning of the mastered units, correct pronunciation and spelling.

The latter requirement can be fulfilled by conducting different types of dictionary dictations. For example, when organizing picture dictation, visual clarity is used, and in this case, the recording mechanism is based on self-dictation. Vocabulary spelling is recommended to be carried out on thematically connected material, so that later it uses written words in the construction of words and sentences.

Students can also be involved in this type of spelling, who determine the content of the thematic dictionary during independent work and prepare to dictate words to their fellow students in the audience by practicing pronunciation skills.

Constant monitoring of students' written speech, methodical correction of individual work with students to identify the causes of certain errors, their elimination and prevention is a necessary condition for the formation of competent written speech in English.

A specific set of written assignments is combined with goal setting for design. It can be built by keywords, by given initialization, by schema, etc. Such exercises are more related to the work related to the development of speech, the methodology of their organization and conduct has its own characteristics, such as the issue of constructing a coherent text, which can be the subject of research in a separate article.

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